

Light-scattering Studies of Tungstic Acid in Ethanol-water Medium

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Tungstic acid, prepared by ion-exchange method in ethanol-water medium, undergoes polymerisation which has been followed by measuring the intensity of scattered light. Along with turbidity, the change in dissymmetry, particle size, and the weight-average molecular weight at different stages of condensation have been measured. The tungstic acid particles have been found to be rod-shaped.

It has been shown recently by the present authors that tungstic acid, prepared by ion-exchange method in ethanol-water medium, undergoes polymerisation and the reaction is of the third order¹. Presence of ethanol slows down the reaction and hence it becomes possible to determine the increase in turbidity, dissymmetry, shape, size, and molecular weight of the particles by the light-scattering method at different stages of polymerisation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Tungstic Acid in Ethanol-water Medium.— $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ of A.R. quality of E. Merck was used as the starting material. The resin, Amberlite I. R.-120 (H), was of analytical grade of Rohm and Haas Company, Pennsylvania. The method of preparation was the same as described previously¹.

Shapes of Tungstic Acid Particles.—According to Debye², the particle-scattering function³, P_θ , in the case of rod of length L is obtained by summing the contributions:

$$P_\theta = \frac{1}{x} \int_0^{2x} \frac{\sin \omega \delta \omega}{\omega} - \left(\frac{\sin x}{x} \right)^2$$

where $x = KsL/2$ ($K = 2\pi/\lambda'$, where λ' is the wave length of light in the solution and $s = 2 \sin \theta/2$) and ω is the variable over which the integration is made. Of the two methods of using the data from measurements of the angular distribution of light scattering, the one introduced by Zimm⁴ and the other by Doby, we followed the method of the latter.

For the measurement of scattering, Brice-Phoenix Universal Light-scattering Photometer and light of wave length 546 m μ were used since tungstic acid sol in the medium of ethanol and water absorbed very little light between 540 and 600 m μ . The intensity of

1. This Journal, 1962, 39, 795.

2. J. Phys. Chem., 1947, 51, 18.

3. Stacy, "Light-Scattering in Physical Chemistry", Butterworths Scientific Publications, London, 1956, p. 26.

4. J. Chem. Phys., 1948, 16, 1093, 1099.

the scattered light was measured at different angles in the cylindrical cell (having one side frosted). The intensities for these angles were subjected to volume correction for the cell by multiplying by $\sin \theta$ and were normalised to account for the variation due to the resolution of polarised components by dividing by $(1 + \cos^2 \theta)$. Then the ratio of the intensities of the light scattered at a given angle to that scattered at 90° is determined. For the angles used, the observed ratios agreed satisfactorily with that calculated from the theoretical curve⁵ (variation of particle-scattering factor P_θ with x), the particles being assumed to be rod shaped. This will be evident from the plot of P_θ/P_{90} vs x (Fig. 1), where $x = 2\pi(L/\lambda') \sin \theta/2$.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2a

FIG. 2b

Molecular ratio of EtOH to water = 0.2068.

Determination of Turbidity, Dissymmetry, and Size.—The increase in turbidity with time was measured and along with all turbidity measurements, the dissymmetry was always measured. From the dissymmetry value and the theoretical curve⁵ (variation of

5, Doty and Steiner, *ibid.*, 1950, 19, 1211,

the correction factor $1/P_{90}$ with dissymmetry Z , the correction factor was found and multiplication of the apparent turbidity by the correction factor provided the corrected turbidity. With the help of the theoretical curve⁸ (variation of dissymmetry Z with D/λ') for rods and the dissymmetry values obtained at different times, the values of L/λ' , and hence the length L of the particles, was calculated. The results are recorded in Table I and the change of turbidity and dissymmetry with time are shown respectively in Figs. 2a and 2b. Refractive index of the solvent was measured by an Abbe refractometer.

TABLE I

% $\text{WO}_3 = 0.980$. Temp. = 25° . Molecular proportion of EtOH: $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 0.2068$.
 Refractive index (n) of the solvent = 1.3520.

Time.	Turbidity.		Dissymmetry (Z).	L .
	Apparent. (T_a)	Corrected. (T_c)		
24 hr.	0.0117	0.0122	1.060	57m μ
48	0.0204	0.0233	1.198	99
72	0.0315	0.0406	1.386	144
96	0.0439	0.0591	1.459	156
120	0.0592	0.0835	1.532	168
145	0.0753	0.1080	1.563	172
168	0.0904	0.1536	1.686	190
192	0.1454	0.2537	1.893	222
217	0.2104	0.4649	2.113	285

Determination of Molecular Weight by Introducing Correction for Dissymmetry and Depolarisation.—In the case of non-ideal solutions, Debye has derived the following equation for relatively small particles:

$$\frac{HC}{T} = \frac{1}{M} + 2BC \quad \dots (1)$$

where H and B are constants, C is the concentration of the solute in g./ml, T is the turbidity, and M is the molecular weight. The constant B depends on the solute-solvent interaction⁹. In practice, H is determined by refraction measurements and T is measured for a series of concentrations and then HC/T is plotted as a function of C and the intercept of the straight line on the ordinate is equal to $1/M$. The molecular weight of tungstic acid was determined at two different stages of the polymerisation process. To evaluate H of equation (1), the refractive index increment was measured in a Brice-Phoenix Differential Refractometer and the value of $\Delta n/C$ was found as 0.1164. The plot of HC/T vs C

FIG. 3

and the value of $\Delta n/C$ was found as 0.1164. The plot of HC/T vs C

is shown in Fig. 3. The molecular weight is corrected from depolarisation measurement by multiplying with the Cabannes factor²:

$$\frac{6}{6} \frac{-}{+} \frac{7\rho_u}{3\rho_v}$$

DISCUSSION

The mechanism of condensation of tungstic acid molecules in ethanol-water medium has been discussed in the previous communication¹. The shape has been determined for a solution, in which the molecular proportion of ethanol to water is 0.167, at 120 and 168 hours after the preparation of the acid. The particles of tungstic acid are found to be rod shaped. It may be mentioned that the electron micrograph of tungstic acid particles, taken by Watson *et al.*⁶, shows that these are needle-shaped. The turbidity, dissymmetry, size, and molecular weight measurements have been made with a solution in which the molecular ratio of ethanol to water is 0.2068. The weight-average molecular weight has been found to be 2.198×10^6 at 53 hours and 19.23×10^6 at 192 hours after the preparation and when corrected for depolarisation, the values are 2.175×10^6 and 17.40×10^6 respectively. Because the time available for each set of measurements is limited, the dissymmetry values (Table I) are not intrinsic values. Therefore the lengths calculated are not absolute values.

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